

GitHub Concepts

GitHub - Concepts

- **Git** - is an open source program for tracking changes in text files.
- **GitHub** - is a repository hosting service for Git, and it provides a web-based graphical interface that works on top of GIT. It can also be treated as a social platform to share knowledge and work;
- **Branch** - is a parallel version of a repository. It is contained within the repository, but does not affect the primary or master branch allowing you to work freely without disrupting the "live" version.
- **Commits** - is an individual change to a file (or set of files). When you make a commit to save your work, Git creates a unique ID (a.k.a. the "SHA" or "hash") that allows you to keep record of the specific changes committed along with who made them and when. Commits usually contain a commit message which is a brief description of what changes were made.

GitHub - Concepts

- **Contributor** - is someone who does not have collaborator access to a repository but has contributed to a project and had a pull request they opened merged into the repository.
- **Fork** - is a personal copy of another user's repository that lives on your account. Forks allow you to freely make changes to a project without affecting the original upstream repository.
- **Pull Requests** - It initiates discussion about your commits or changes made to a code. When you open a pull request, you're proposing your changes and requesting that someone review and pull in your contribution and merge them into their branch.
- **Merge** - It takes the changes from one branch (in the same repository or from a fork), and applies them into another.

GitHub - Concepts

- **Issues** - are suggested improvements, tasks or questions related to the repository. Issues can be created by anyone (for public repositories), and are moderated by repository collaborators.
- **README** - A text file containing information about the files in a repository.
- **Repository** - is the most basic element of GitHub. They're easiest to imagine as a project's folder. A repository contains all of the project files (including documentation), and stores each file's revision history. Repositories can have multiple collaborators and can be either public or private.

GitHub Concepts

